

BASKETBALL ELEMENTS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

There are several ways to optimize the training process using various complexes of exercises, dynamic games and much more in physical education in school, including the primary level. At the same time, in recent years, sports games have become more and more popular, especially the game of basketball, which is quite attractive and dynamic, and quite popular among students.

According to the physical education school curriculum, sports games, including basketball, are mainly taught in primary school. However, it is relevant to use different elements of sports games in the primary stage, in our case the game of basketball, these being possible to apply more in the form of dynamic games.

This is the direction that has been the subject of our research, meaning the widespread application of dynamic games with elements of the basketball game in physical education lessons with students in the primary stage.

Keywords: students, primary school, basketball elements

Subject’s actuality. According to the data of the specialized literature [1, 4, 6, 7], the young school age is very important for the development of children not only from a motor but also a functional point of view. The age of 7-11 years is a large part of the sensitive periods of development of motor skills, meaning the most favourable periods for the development of one or another quality.

There are several ways to optimize the training process using various complexes of exercises, dynamic games and much more in physical education in school, including the primary level. At the same time, in recent years, sports games have become more and more popular, especially the game of basketball, which is quite attractive and dynamic, and quite popular among students.

According to the physical education school curriculum, sports games, including basketball, are mainly taught in high school. However, it is relevant to use different elements of sports games in the primary stage, in our case the game of basketball, these being possible to apply more in the form of dynamic games [2, 3, 5].

This is what we are particularly interested in, namely the widespread application of dynamic games with elements of the game of basketball in physical education lessons with primary school students.

Therefore, **the purpose of the study** is to research the effectiveness of applying the complexes of dynamic games with elements of the game of basketball to physical education lessons with primary school students.

Research methods and techniques used. In order to successfully achieve the objectives of the expected research, a series of quite known methods and techniques in physical education have been applied, such as:

- Analysis of bibliographic sources
- testing method
- pedagogical experiment
- statistical-mathematical methods

In order to achieve the proposed goal, a one-year pedagogical experiment was organized for second-grade students, aged between 8 and 9, from the Theoretical High School "Mihail Sadoveanu" in Chisinau, where they were using mostly complex dynamic games with elements of the basketball game.

The elements of the basketball game that we used are provided in the physical education curriculum for the 5th-grade students and can be successfully used in the primary classes as well.

Below is a classification and more examples of dynamic games used in the experiment. We mention that the description of the games used can be largely found in several works of specialists from the country and abroad. Next, we will present the diagram of selection and classification of dynamic games with elements from the basketball game in physical education lessons with primary school students (fig. 1.).

Thus, the dynamic games that we projected to apply in the training process of primary school students are classified into two large groups, these being indoor games and outdoor games. All these games have in turn a concrete destination, this being the qualitative learning of the procedures and technical elements in the game of basketball, characteristic of that age.

Fig. 1. Classification of dynamic games with basketball elements

Ultimately, the games can be selected according to the objectives envisaged by the teaching staff, here referring to the compartment *they want to address*, being technical training, physical training and tactical training. It is clear that in our case most of the games were selected and used for technical training, *namely* for learning the technical elements of the basketball game.

It is worth mentioning that this classification was used not only during the pedagogical experiment but also throughout the school year when it came to learning the game of basketball.

One of the main components related to the preparation of students in the primary stage (the 2nd grade) for the lesson of sports games (basketball) is the technical training. In other words, the level of mastery of the procedures and technical elements in the game of basketball. According to the school curriculum in the discipline "physical education", *the basketball compartment is* expected to acquire several elements and technical procedures. Speaking of the basic technical elements with the ball, here we can list the following: passes, throws, and dribbling.

In pedagogical practice, there are several methodical procedures for training students in mastering the game of basketball. One of the most effective, in our opinion, is the widespread use of dynamic games with elements of the game of basketball in specialized lessons in this game. Namely, this methodical procedure was applied with the second-grade students from the Theoretical High School “Mihail Sadoveanu” from Chisinau within a formative pedagogical experiment.

In this context, at the beginning and end of the semester of studies lasting one year, where the dynamic games with elements from the basketball game were used (according to the annual work plan), it was organized the testing of second-grade students on mastering the elements and technical procedures from the basketball game which are listed above. It was established a block of 4 tests, namely:

- Dribbling the ball avoiding the circles
- Passing the ball into the wall in 30 sec
- Throws into the basket from 5 positions
- Throws into the basket from the standard position

Speaking about the level of mastering of the technical elements of the game, it is worth mentioning that the tasks were performed by boys and girls together; therefore, the mastering of the game technique does not differ much whether the participants are boys or girls. (Table 1., Fig. 1.)

The first control exercise, called a test, was "dribbling the ball around the circles", where the average of the group at the beginning of the experiment was 40.62 seconds, and at the end of the experiment the ground travel period bypassing the circles decreased to 37,41 seconds.

Analyzing the results recorded in this test, we are noticing that at the end of the pedagogical experiment the tested indicators increased significantly, this being clearly demonstrated by statistical calculations, the difference between initial and final testing being statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). This clearly demonstrates that the application of the experimental methodology and the widespread use of dynamic games with elements of the basketball game has had an impressive impact on the mastering of a basic element of the basketball game, such as dribbling. This is very visibly shown in Figure 1.

Table 1. The results of assimilation of the technical elements of the basketball game of the primary school students

N. or	Technical elements	Initial testing	Final testing	Control rule
1.	Dribbling the ball avoiding the circles	44,62± 0,33	37,41 ± 0,27	<0.05
2.	Passing to the wall in 20 s, no. rep.	17,43± 0,28	19,28±0,32	<0.01
3.	Throwing into the basket from 5 positions, no. successful	3,14 ±0,40	4,27±0,23	<0.05
4.	Throwing into the basket from the standard position	3,45 ± 0,05	3,82±0,04	<0.05

Fig 1. The results of mastering the technical elements of the game of basketball of the primary school students

Regarding the technical test "passing the ball to the wall in 20s", the students of the group involved in the experiment at the beginning of the year showed an average result of 17.43 birds. At the end of the pedagogical experiment, we are recording an increase of this indicator by about two passes more, reaching the average of 29.28 birds for 20 seconds.

If we analyze the results recorded in this test, we notice that at the end of the pedagogical experiment the tested indicators increased relatively much, this being clearly demonstrated by statistical calculations, the difference between initial and final testing being statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). These results clearly demonstrate that the widespread use of dynamic games with elements of the basketball game has had an impressive impact on the acquisition of another basic element of the basketball game, such as passing the ball.

Quite interesting were the results at the end of the pedagogical experiment in the test "Throws into the basket from 5 positions", where students were to complete two sets of 5 throws on the perimeter of the square of the three-second restricted area.

At the beginning of the experiment, the group of students recorded an average of 3.14 successful throws from the ten points set, so that at the end of the experiment the results reached values of 4.27 successful.

Following the analysis of the results recorded in this test, we notice that at the end of the pedagogical experiment the tested indicators increased quite a lot, this being clearly demonstrated

by statistical calculations, the difference between initial and final testing being statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). These results demonstrate once again that the widespread use of dynamic games with elements of the basketball game has had an impressive impact on the acquisition of other basic elements of the basketball game, such as passing, and throwing into the basket.

The following test also relates to the assessment of the skill level of the throws into the basket, with the simple difference that in this case the throws are fulfilled from a standard position from a distance of 3 meters from the basket.

Thus, analyzing the initial results of the students involved in the pedagogical experiment at the beginning of the experiment, the students recorded an average of 3.45 exact throws in the basket from the standard position, so that at the end of the experiment the results reach average values of 3.82.

Analyzing the results recorded in this test, we notice that at the end of the pedagogical experiment the tested indicators increased relatively much, this being clearly demonstrated by statistical calculations, the difference between initial and final testing being statistically significant ($P < 0,05$). These results demonstrate once again that the widespread use of dynamic games with elements of the basketball game has had an impressive impact on the acquisition of another basic element of the basketball game, such as throwing in the basket, in this case from the standard position.

Therefore, analyzing all the results as a whole, it is clear the successes of the group involved in the pedagogical experiment on mastering the elements and technical procedures provided by the school curriculum at this age. This is primarily due to the application of dynamic games with elements of the basketball game to basketball lessons, which led to the positive transfer of motor skills and abilities, which in turn reflected in the qualitative acquisition of the game technique, the fact demonstrated by concrete results in this regard.

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